

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

Volume I Issue VII

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**
A Creative Folio

NOVEMBER 2025
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
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Butuan City, Philippines
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Volume I, Issue VII (November 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

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[DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17591209](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17591209)

Mental Health Issues: Fighting till the END

Nowadays, teenagers and maybe some kids have issues with their mental health that put their lives at risk.

Mental health is something important to us, and we need to maintain good Mental health for our safety. People who do not have good mental health may resort to suicide, leaving their family and friends awful.

Bullying, family issues, and traumatic events are some things that can cause problems in our mental health. We can prevent issues by getting enough rest, staying connected to our loved ones, and seeking professional help when needed.

We must prevent bullying and also cyberbullying at all costs because it harms others' mental health. Bullying others won't make you happy, but it makes others unhappy.

It doesn't matter what others think about you; always think positively and be confident in yourself. The person you're always with is yourself; keep that on your mind.

Always express what you are experiencing and never stay quiet, talk about your issues because it lets them know what pain you are experiencing, what battle you are fighting.

Never stop fighting for yourself; fight until the end and keep battling. Don't give up, keep on getting up.